

ENABLING FASTER STRUCTURAL DESIGN: EFFICIENT MULTISCALE SIMULATION OF LARGE COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A novel set of Periodic Boundary Conditions named Multiscale Periodic Boundary Conditions (MPBCs) that apply to *reduced* Unit Cells (rUCs) and enable the two-scale (solid-to-shell) numerical homogenization of periodic structures, including their bending and twisting response, is presented and implemented in an FE code. Reduced Unit Cells are domains smaller than the Unit Cells (UCs), obtained by exploiting the internal symmetries of the UCs. Using the MPBCs it is possible to correctly simulate the mechanical response of periodic structures using rUCs (retrieving the same results as if conventional UCs were used), thus enabling a significant reduction of both modelling/meshing ($\approx -85\%$) and analysis ($\approx -89\%$) CPU times. These results demonstrate the relevance of the proposed approach for an efficient multiscale modelling of periodic materials and structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Recent experiences in aeronautics (such as Boeing's 787 three-year delayed début and over 12B\$ over budget) show that the current difficulties with design and manufacture may jeopardize the share of composites in future structures. This paper addresses the issue of using accurate unit cell models to efficiently predict the performance of large aeronautical components.

Owing to the heterogeneous micro-structure of composite materials, the applicability of conventional FE analyses based on 3D (solid) models is limited to small components; 2D (shell) FE models with equivalent homogenised properties are preferable for larger components. Furthermore, for the efficient structural design of large composite components, the numerical analysis of their mechanical response often requires different parts of the structure to be modelled at multiple length/time-scales. Hence, see Fig. 1, it is crucial to develop (i) suitable techniques for coupling areas of the structure discretized using different finite element types and (ii) numerical methods to efficiently compute equivalent homogenized properties to be used in both 2D FE models and in the coarse-scale subdomains of multiscale FE models of large composite components.

Regarding the first point, a novel local/global coupling approach based on a Mesh Superposition Technique (MST) for the progressive transition between subdomains modelled at different length-scales and whose response is analysed at different time-scales has been recently presented by the authors [1]. This paper focuses on the second remaining point.

Numerical homogenization of periodic structures and materials commonly involves the analysis of Unit Cell (UC) models in which the structure is explicitly resolved at the lowest length-scale; several studies on the existence and size of suitable UCs are available in literature [2, 3]. However, for several practical cases, e.g. textile composites and pin-reinforced composite sandwich structures, the topological complexity of the representative UCs may lead to unaffordable modelling/meshing and analysis CPU times. Therefore, the internal symmetries of the UCs should, whenever they exist, be exploited to reduce the analysis domain, thus enabling a reduction of both the modelling/meshing and analysis CPU times.

Figure 1: Multiple length/time-scales simulation of large composite aeronautical components. This work addresses the issues of (i) coupling areas of large composite structures discretized using different finite element types [1] and (ii) exploiting symmetries for the solid-to-shell homogenization of periodic structures.

Domains smaller than the UCs, obtained by exploiting the internal symmetries of the latter, are referred to as *reduced* Unit Cells (rUCs). Several works can be found discussing the determination of suitable rUCs (and corresponding appropriate PBCs) for UD composites [4], particle-reinforced composites [5] and textile composites [6, 7]. The PBCs proposed in these studies allow the determination of the homogenised 3D elasticity tensor of the investigated structure. Nevertheless, for the numerical analysis of large components using equivalent shell models, it is of interest to determine the homogenised shell constitutive response of the structure using high-fidelity three-dimensional UCs or, preferably, rUCs.

To address this, we present a novel set of PBCs named Multiscale Periodic Boundary Conditions (MPBCs), that represents the first set of PBCs that apply to rUCs and enable the direct two-scale (solid-to-shell) numerical homogenization of periodic structures, including their bending and twisting response. The proposed MPBCs are formulated in Sect. 2.2 while details on their use within the context of a solid-to-shell homogenization and on their FE implementation are provided in Sect. 2.3 and Sect. 3, respectively. The MPCBs are applied to the analysis of the mechanical response of a periodic sandwich structure with unequal skins and pin-reinforced core in Sect. 4. Conclusions are drawn in Sect. 5.

2 THEORY

2.1 Problem formulation

Consider a three-dimensional deformable body \mathcal{B}_3 occupying the domain $\mathcal{D}_3 \in \mathbb{R}^3$, as shown in Fig. 2, and assume that one of the dimensions of \mathcal{D}_3 , designated as the thickness (denoted as h), is much smaller than the other two. Furthermore, let \mathcal{D}_3 be periodic in the plane normal to the thickness direction. For reasons of numerical efficiency, the macroscopic mechanical response of \mathcal{B}_3 is more conveniently simulated by means of an equivalent shell model with homogenized properties contained in $\mathcal{D}_2 \in \mathbb{R}^2$. The corresponding shell constitutive response can be expressed by the relation $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{K}\xi_o$, where \mathbf{R} is the vector of resultant forces/moments per unit-length acting on the structure, ξ_o is the resultant mid-surface membrane strains/curvatures vector and the \mathbf{K} matrix (referred to, in lamination theory, as the **ABD** matrix) contains the equivalent shell stiffness terms.

Therefore, the accurate determination of the entire \mathbf{K} matrix, including all bending and twisting terms, as well as the shear-extension, bending-extension and bending-twisting coupling terms, is of paramount importance for the use of equivalent shell models of large composite components.

2.2 Multiscale Periodic Boundary Conditions (MPBCs)

The homogenized 2D response of a three-dimensional periodic structure can be evaluated through the analysis of three-dimensional UCs/rUCs modelled at the meso-scale, provided the appropriate PBCs are applied to its boundaries. These PBCs, referred to in the following as Multiscale PBCs (MPBCs), are prescribed such that the three-dimensional UC/rUC behaves as it were contained in an infinite body \mathcal{B}_3 (in domain \mathcal{D}_3) whose macroscopic response can be analysed using shell theory (in domain \mathcal{D}_2).

Assume that domain \mathcal{D}_3 can be reconstructed from the tessellation of repeating UCs, as schematically shown in Fig. 3; in addition, let these UCs have internal symmetries, which if exploited lead to the definition of rUCs (see Fig. 3). Moreover, let $\mathfrak{s} \in \mathcal{D}_3$ and $\hat{\mathfrak{s}} \in \mathcal{D}_3$ be two adjacent subdomains satisfying both the physical and loading equivalence and let \mathfrak{s} be a suitable rUC [8]. Furthermore, denote with $[O, \mathbf{e}_i]_{\mathfrak{s}}$ and $[\hat{O}, \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i]_{\hat{\mathfrak{s}}}$ the Local Coordinate Systems (LCSs) of subdomains \mathfrak{s} and $\hat{\mathfrak{s}}$, respectively, and define the two-dimensional symmetry transformation matrix between $[O, \mathbf{e}_i]_{\mathfrak{s}}$ and $[\hat{O}, \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i]_{\hat{\mathfrak{s}}}$ as $\mathbf{T} = \{T_{ij}\}$ where $T_{ii} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{e}_i}{\partial \hat{\mathbf{e}}_i}$ with $i \in \{1, 2\}$ and $T_{ij} = 0$ if $i \neq j$. In the following, the coordinate values along the direction \mathbf{e}_i are indicated as x_i .

Consider now two equivalent points $A \in \mathfrak{s}$ and $\hat{A} \in \hat{\mathfrak{s}}$ (see Fig. 3); if A is at the boundary of \mathfrak{s} , i.e.

Figure 2: Problem formulation. The macroscopic response of the periodic domain \mathcal{D}_3 can be simulated by means of an equivalent shell model, provided the equivalent 2D constitutive response of a representative three-dimensional UC/rUC (subdomain s) is correctly determined.

$A \in \partial s$, then also $\hat{A} \in \partial s$. Under these premises, the proposed MPBCs can be expressed as [8]

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u}(A) - \gamma \mathbf{T} \mathbf{u}(\hat{A}) &= \left[\langle \nabla \mathbf{u}_o \rangle - (T_{33} x_3^{\hat{A}}) \langle \nabla \nabla w_o \rangle \right] \mathbf{T} [(O\hat{A})_o - (O\hat{O})_o] + [\mathbf{I} - \gamma \mathbf{T}] \mathbf{u}(O) + \\ &- \gamma \mathbf{T} \left[\langle \nabla \mathbf{u}_o \rangle - x_3^{\hat{A}} \langle \nabla \nabla w_o \rangle \right] (O\hat{A})_o \quad \forall x_3^{\hat{A}} \in \left[-\frac{h}{2}, \frac{h}{2} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} w(A) - \gamma T_{33} w(\hat{A}) &= [(O\hat{A})_o - (O\hat{O})_o]^t \mathbf{T} \left[\frac{\langle \nabla \nabla w_o \rangle}{2} \right] \mathbf{T} [(O\hat{A})_o - (O\hat{O})_o] + [1 - \gamma T_{33}] w(O) + \\ &- \gamma T_{33} (O\hat{A})_o^t \left[\frac{\langle \nabla \nabla w_o \rangle}{2} \right] (O\hat{A})_o \quad \forall x_3^{\hat{A}} \in \left[-\frac{h}{2}, \frac{h}{2} \right], \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\mathbf{u} = \{u, v\}^t$ is the in-plane displacement vector, w the out-of-plane displacement, $\gamma = \pm 1$ the load reversal factor [8], \mathbf{I} the 2×2 identity matrix and $x_3^{\hat{A}}$ the out-of-plane coordinate of point \hat{A} . In Eqs. 1-2, the superscript t indicates the transpose of a tensor, the subscript o denotes quantities evaluated at the mid-surface of the UC/rUC and $\langle \bullet \rangle = \frac{1}{V_s} \int_{V_s} (\bullet) dV$ denotes the volume average operator over domain s .

Figure 3: The periodic domain \mathcal{D}_3 can be reconstructed by tessellation of repeating Unit Cells (UCs): UC's internal symmetries, if they exist, can be exploited for defining reduced Unit Cells.

The membrane deformation tensor $\nabla \mathbf{u}_o$ and the curvature tensor $\nabla \nabla w_o$ are defined, respectively, as

$$\nabla \mathbf{u}_o = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial x_2} \\ \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial x_1} & \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial x_2} \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla \nabla w_o = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial^2 w_o}{\partial x_1^2} & \frac{\partial^2 w_o}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} \\ \frac{\partial^2 w_o}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} & \frac{\partial^2 w_o}{\partial x_2^2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

The following aspects of the proposed MPBCs can be highlighted:

- the proposed formulation is valid for both conventional UCs and, more relevantly, for rUCs. Secondly, no limitations on the undeformed shape of the UC/rUC are assumed, therefore, complex UC/rUC geometries can be considered;
- no limitations on the deformed shape of the UC/rUC were hypothesized. Hence, the *plane-remains-plane* boundary conditions [9, 10], which have been proven to be over-constraining [11], as well as to violate the stress-strain periodicity condition [12], are avoided;
- since no periodicity exists in the thickness direction, the MPBCs are applied only on the lateral faces of the UC/rUC; in addition, as a result of the plane-stress assumption of shell theory, the upper and lower faces of the UC/rUC are traction-free;
- the MPBCs are expressed in terms of the relative displacement between equivalent points belonging to the boundary of the UC/rUC. This approach is supported by the results presented in [13] which demonstrate that imposing equilibrium and/or compatibility equations as part of the boundary conditions, see e.g. [14], is not only unnecessary but it also violates the minimum total potential energy principle;
- no *a priori* restrictions to the nonlinear behaviour at the lowest length-scale were made (provided there is no localization [15]);
- the presented MPBCs can be used for the two-scale (3D-2D) homogenization of any microstructure, regardless of its complexity, and any loading components can be prescribed to the UC/rUC, including bending and twisting.

2.3 Two-scale (solid-to-shell) homogenisation of periodic structures

Provided the MPBCs are applied to all points on the lateral boundary of the three-dimensional UC/rUC, the 2D constitutive response, i.e. all terms of the equivalent shell stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} , can be determined by sequentially subjecting the UC/rUC to the six conventional loadings of shell theory, i.e. membrane stretching, membrane shearing, bending and twisting, see Fig. 2. These are applied by specifying the components of $\langle \nabla \mathbf{u}_o \rangle$ for the macroscopic membrane deformations, and of $\langle \nabla \nabla w_o \rangle$ for the bending and twisting curvatures. In the remaining, all quantities are evaluated in the LCS of the UC/rUC; the corresponding subscripts and superscripts will be omitted hereafter for convenience.

The components of $\langle \nabla \mathbf{u}_o \rangle$ and of $\langle \nabla \nabla w_o \rangle$ can be related to the membrane strains and curvatures adopted in shell theory as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_o^1 &=: \left\langle \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial x_1} \right\rangle, & \varepsilon_o^2 &=: \left\langle \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial x_2} \right\rangle, & \gamma_o^{12} &=: \left\langle \frac{\partial u_o}{\partial x_2} \right\rangle + \left\langle \frac{\partial v_o}{\partial x_1} \right\rangle \\ \kappa_o^1 &=: \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 w_o}{\partial x_1^2} \right\rangle, & \kappa_o^2 &=: \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 w_o}{\partial x_2^2} \right\rangle, & \kappa_o^{12} &=: 2 \left\langle \frac{\partial^2 w_o}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} \right\rangle \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where ε_o^1 and ε_o^2 are the membrane direct strains, γ_o^{12} is the membrane shear strain, κ_o^1 and κ_o^2 are the bending curvatures and κ_o^{12} is the twisting curvature.

The 2D equivalent strains/curvatures vector $\xi_o = [\varepsilon_o^1, \varepsilon_o^2, \gamma_o^{12}, \kappa_o^1, \kappa_o^2, \kappa_o^{12}]^t$ can be related to the vector of the equivalent forces/moments per unit length $\mathbf{R} = [N_1, N_2, N_{12}, M_1, M_2, M_{12}]^t$, through the tensor equation $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{K} \xi_o$ or, in its expanded form:

$$\begin{bmatrix} N_1 \\ N_2 \\ N_{12} \\ \text{---} \\ M_1 \\ M_2 \\ M_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & | & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ & A_{22} & A_{26} & | & & B_{22} & B_{16} \\ \text{sym} & & A_{66} & | & \text{sym} & & B_{66} \\ \text{---} & \text{---} & \text{---} & \text{---} & \text{---} & \text{---} & \text{---} \\ & & & | & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ & \text{sym} & & | & & D_{22} & D_{16} \\ & & & | & \text{sym} & & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \varepsilon_o^1 \\ \varepsilon_o^2 \\ \gamma_o^{12} \\ \text{---} \\ \kappa_o^1 \\ \kappa_o^2 \\ \kappa_o^{12} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (5)$$

The \mathbf{K} matrix can be determined according to either of the two procedures:

Procedure A- by prescribing a non-zero value to the i -th term of ξ_o (while fixing the remaining terms to zero), all terms of \mathbf{R} are, in the most general case, non-zero. Therefore, from Eq. 5 the i -th column of the \mathbf{K} matrix is proportional to the vector of generalized forces that is obtained from the solution of the FE problem. Repeating the same procedure for all six components of ε_o , the entire \mathbf{K} matrix can be computed;

Procedure B- by prescribing a non-zero value to the i -th term of ξ_o (while letting the remaining terms unconstrained), all terms but the i -th of \mathbf{R} are equal to zero. Hence, the i -th column of the compliance matrix $\mathbf{C} = \mathbf{K}^{-1}$ ($\xi_o = \mathbf{C} \mathbf{R}$) is proportional to the vector of generalized displacements that is obtained from the solution of the FE problem. Repeating the same procedure for all six components of ξ_o , the entire \mathbf{C} matrix can be computed, and by inverting the latter, the \mathbf{K} matrix can be determined.

3 FE IMPLEMENTATION

Concerning the FE implementation of the proposed MPBCs, let us consider a discretized UC/rUC as the one shown in Fig. 4a. The MPBCs, expressed for the continuum case in the form of Eqs. 1 -2, are enforced through constraint equations (CEs) acting on equivalent nodes on the boundary of the UC/rUC (see e.g. nodes \mathcal{A} and $\hat{\mathcal{A}}$ in Fig. 4b). Since they are based on a node-to-node coupling, the application of the MPBCs is ideally suited for a periodic discretization along the boundary of the UC/rUC.

The terms of ξ_{\circ} are prescribed by specifying the degrees of freedom (DOFs) of master nodes that do not belong to the mesh of the UC/rUC. In principle, a single master node \mathcal{M} with at least six DOFs is sufficient for this purpose. Regarding the terms of the generalized forces vector \mathbf{R} , these simply correspond to the reaction forces/moments at node \mathcal{M} . Therefore, assuming that the i -th component of ξ_{\circ} is associated to the j -th DOF of node \mathcal{M} , the i -th term of \mathbf{R} corresponds to the j -th reaction force/moment at node \mathcal{M} .

Figure 4: FE implementation of the MPBCs. The DOFs of equivalent nodes on the boundary of the UC/rUC are coupled using constraint equations; the external loading are specified through the DOFs of the master node \mathcal{M} which does not belong to the mesh of the UC/rUC.

The MPBCs have been implemented in the Finite Element (FE) package Abaqus (6.12) [16] through the in-built Python scripting facilities. The simulations have been performed using Abaqus/Standard, and linear geometric behaviour was used in the example that follows.

4 SOLID-TO-SHELL HOMOGENIZATION: PERIODIC PIN-REINFORCED SANDWICH STRUCTURE

4.1 Description

The aim of this application example is to demonstrate that the current formulation enables to correctly simulate the mechanical response of periodic structures using rUCs (retrieving the same results as if conventional UCs were used but at a fraction of the CPU time). To this purpose, the MPBCs have been applied for the analysis of the mechanical response of a periodic sandwich structure with unequal skins and pin-reinforced core.

Table 1: Elastic properties, density and thickness of the NCF triaxial weave [19].

E_{11}	$E_{22}=E_{33}$	$G_{12}=G_{13}=G_{23}$	ρ
54.7 GPa	9.0 GPa	23.3 GPa	1600 kg/m ³
ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}	h_w
0.73	0.26	0.45	0.375 mm

Table 2: Elastic properties and density of the HERO G3 150 foam [18].

E_f	ν_f	ρ_f
127.5 MPa	0.33	150 kg/m ³

The facesheets material is composed of multiple layers of Saertex triaxial weave with Toho Tenax HTS carbon fibres and a polyester knitting yarn, infused with RTM6 epoxy resin [17]. The layout of the individual Non-Crimp Fabric (NCF) weaves is $[45^\circ/0^\circ/-45^\circ]$ and their material properties are listed in Table 1 along with their thickness h_w . The core material is the closed-cell polymetacrylimide foam Rohacell HERO 150 [18], whose elastic properties and density are provided in Table 2. The thicknesses of the individual layers of the sandwich structure, along with the layouts for the top and bottom facesheets are provided in Table 3. Here, h_f^t and h_f^b are, respectively, the thickness of the top and bottom facesheet, and h_c is the thickness of the foam core; furthermore, the individual NCF weave orientations are defined relatively to their 0° -plies.

The reinforcements consist of CFRP pins made of dry intermediate modulus (IM7 12K) [20] carbon fibres infiltrated with RTM6 epoxy resin during the manufacturing of the sandwich panel [21]; the resulting elastic modulus in the fibre direction is $E_{\text{pin}} = 126$ GPa. The pins are inserted through the foam core (without going through or penetrate the facesheets) in a periodic pattern, see the UC in Fig. 5. As shown the latter, the UC can be reconstructed by tessellation of smaller subdomains (rUCs), by exploiting internal symmetries; in this example, the analysis is performed using the rUC highlighted in green in Fig. 5. The geometrical parameters of the rUC are provided in Table 4. Here, φ and β are, respectively, the through-the-thickness and in-plane stitching angles (see Fig. 5); ℓ_1 and ℓ_2 are the in-plane dimensions of the rUC and ϕ is the diameter of the pin-reinforcements.

The facesheets and the core were discretized using eight-noded reduced integration solid elements (C3D8R) with enhanced hourglass control, and a constant element size $\ell_s = 0.375$ mm was adopted; the interfaces between different plies and between the facesheets and the core were not explicitly modelled, i.e. they share nodes. The pin-reinforcements were discretized with two-noded linear beam elements (B31); to simplify the meshing of the pin-reinforced core, the pins' finite elements were embedded within the foam core exploiting the Embedded Element Method (EEM) available in Abaqus. This method has been already used for modelling pin-reinforced cores [22] and textile composites [23]. The optimal ratio between the embedded beam elements' size ℓ_e and the hosting elements' size ℓ_h , i.e. $\alpha = \frac{\ell_e}{\ell_h}$ was determined so to avoid the characteristic artificial stiffness [24] resulting from the EEM implementation. In this example, the value of $\alpha = 1$ was adopted.

The sandwich structure was subjected to a twisting loading, i.e. $\kappa_o^{12} = 10^{-3}$ rad/mm and the reference solution for this problem was obtained using the entire UC (see Fig. 5). It is worth-noting that, when using the latter, the MPBCs reduce to the standard PBCs already used by other authors [25, 26].

4.2 Results and discussion

The in-plane strains (e_{11}, e_{22}, e_{12}) evaluated along the path shown in Fig. 5 (red dotted line A-B passing through the center of the UC), computed with the rUC and the UC models are compared, respectively,

Table 3: Sandwich layers' thicknesses and facesheets layups.

h_f^t	h_f^b	h_c	Top skin Layup	Bottom skin Layup
3.0 mm	3.0 mm	10.5 mm	$[0^\circ/30^\circ/60^\circ, 90^\circ]_s$	$[15^\circ/45^\circ/75^\circ, -15^\circ]_s$

Figure 5: Schematic of the UC and rUC considered for the analysis of the mechanical response of a periodic sandwich structure with unequal skins and pin-reinforced core. The UC's internal symmetries are exploited for the definition of the rUC (in green). The red dotted line A-B indicates the path along which the membrane strains distribution, computed with the UC and the rUC models, have been compared.

in Figs. 6a, 6b and 6c. These strain values are extracted at each element's integration point.

The total CPU time t associated to the analyses using the rUC and the UC models are compared in Fig. 7a. In addition, results are provided in terms of both the modelling/meshing CPU time t_M needed for the Python script to create the FE model and apply the suitable MPBCs (Fig. 7b), and the analysis CPU time t_A needed to perform the FE analyses (Fig. 7c). The CPU times provided in Fig. 7 have been normalized with respect to the values associated with the analysis performed using the UC model, respectively, t^{uc} , t_M^{uc} and t_A^{uc} .

Since the discretizations of the UC and rUC models are the same, as expected, the membrane strains distributions computed with these models are identical; this demonstrate that, through the correct appli-

Table 4: Geometrical parameters defining the rUC of the periodic structure with unequal skins and pin-reinforced core.

$l_1 = l_2$	ϕ	φ	β
10.125 mm	1.0 mm	60°	45°

(c) Membrane shear strain e_{12} .

Figure 6: Membrane strains distributions in the UC and rUC models along the path A-B shown in Fig. 5 under twisting load. Since the discretizations of the UC and rUC models are the same, the strains distributions computed with the UC and the rUC models are, as expected, identical.

cation of the proposed MPBCs, the mechanical response of periodic structures can be analysed using domains smaller than the Unit Cell, while maintaining the same level of accuracy.

Compared to the UC model, the rUC model has, approximately, 25% of the degrees of freedom (DOFs) and 50% of the constraint equations (CEs). These attributes lead to a reduction of the total CPU time of about 87% (see Fig. 7a); the latter hinges on the reduction of both the modelling/meshing CPU time ($\approx -85\%$) and the analysis CPU time ($\approx -89\%$), as shown in Figs. 7b and 7c, respectively.

Figure 7: The MPCs enable the use of rUCs for the analysis of the mechanical response of periodic structures. This translates into a reduction of the total CPU time required (a), as a result of the reduction of both the modelling/meshing CPU time t_M needed to create the FE model and apply the suitable MPBCs (b) and the analysis CPU time t_A necessary to run the FE analysis (c).

Although these specific values are, admittedly, dependent on the model's size and on the specific analysis performed, they confirm the capabilities of the approach proposed in this paper.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a novel set of Multiscale Periodic Boundary Conditions (MPBCs) enabling the direct two-scale (solid-to-shell) numerical homogenization of periodic structures, including their bending and twisting response, using domains smaller than the Unit Cells (UCs), named reduced Unit Cells (rUCs), is presented. The MPCs are applied to the analysis of the mechanical response of a periodic sandwich structure with unequal skins and pin-reinforced core, using a rUC. The results show that the use of the proposed MPBCs allows to correctly simulate the mechanical response of periodic structures using rUCs, retrieving the same results as if conventional UCs were adopted.

When compared to MPBCs which do not exploit symmetries, the MPBCs presented in this paper are shown to achieve a significant reduction in analysis time (approximately 89%), as well as modelling/meshing time (over 85%). These results demonstrate the relevance of the proposed approach for an efficient multiscale modelling of periodic materials and structures.

Finally, if used in combination with suitable global/local coupling techniques such as the Mesh Superposition Technique (MST) proposed by the authors [1], the MPBCs enable the efficient multiscale simulation of large composite aeronautical components (see Fig. 1), otherwise computationally unaffordable with standard 3D FE models, or inaccurate with conventional 2D FE models with equivalent homogenised properties.

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